

PATTERNS AND CORRELATES OF INVIGILATOR - EXAMINATION MISCONDUCT CHARACTERISTICS IN SELECTED TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study investigated patterns and correlates of invigilator - examination misconduct characteristics in selected tertiary institutions in Imo state, Nigeria. Based on the purpose of the study, one research question and two hypotheses guided the study. Eighty invigilators were observed during a total of eight semester examinations. The instrument for data collection was a researchers' developed observation Questionnaire entitled 'Examination Invigilation Misconduct Survey' (EIMS). Data were analyzed with frequency counts, mean and t- test statistics. The findings showed that the common misconducts included helping students to answer question, noise making, incessant announcements, and late arrival of invigilators to examinations among others. It was found out that there was no significant effect of gender of invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct. The study however, found a significant effect of invigilators' experience in favour of the more experienced invigilators concerning examination misconducts. It was recommended that the authorities of institutions should periodically provide re-orientation programmes for all lecturers on examination invigilation, prescribe and take disciplinary actions against invigilators who fail to carry out their invigilation responsibilities properly.

Keywords: Invigilator misconduct, Examination misconduct, Tertiary institutions and Patterns of misconduct

Introduction

In most known formal educational institutions, examinations are conducted at some periodic intervals. It may be every term as in the case of primary and secondary schools or every semester as is obtained in most tertiary institutions. These examinations usually called internal examinations are conducted to find out what the pupils or students have learnt in the subjects and courses they have been taught or exposed to. The results of such examinations are used for various purposes. For example, they may be used to promote students from one class or level to the next. They may also be used to classify or stream the students subject based or ability groups. The guidance counsellors equally use examination results to offer help to students having diagnosed students' areas of strengths and weaknesses as well as career inclinations and potentials (Tuta, 2010).

Some examinations are conducted by examination bodies like Examination Development Centre of The Ministry of Education, West African Examinations Council, Joint Admissions and Matriculations Board, National Examinations Council, National Business and Technical Examination Board as well the tertiary institutions. The results of examinations conducted by these organizations are used mainly for selection and certification.

One could therefore, assert that the use and value of examinations are very enormous and immense. That is why both the examiners and the candidates should handle examinations as well as examination matters very seriously. Examinations should be properly conducted. Proper conduct of examinations demands that examination rules and even ethics are adhered to. Proper conduct of examination is expected of both the students and the invigilators. This is because for examination results to be utilized meaningfully, they must be valid and reliable. Regrettably, most examinations are marred by poor conduct leading to various forms of malpractices. The resultant consequence is that selections made and certificates issued on the basis of examination results do not command the credibility expected of them (Ukah and Ukwuoma, 2012). Some studies including (Olaniyi, 2011, Decklan, 2015) had concentrated on students' factors for being responsible for poor conduct of examinations. Some have investigated examination disturbance related behaviour among students and have indicted students for a great number of examination malpractices and misconducts. Some recent studies on examination on examination malpractice (Omugo, Ukah and Ukwuoma, 2019) reported that irrespective of investigations and recommendations made to assuage examination malpractices, there has not been any meaningful decrease in the scale of examination malpractice. The report states that: One of the major factors which may corrupt examination results is examination misconduct. Examination misconduct is a defiance of or non-compliance to rules and regulations as well as the ethics that guide proper conduct of any examination. Sometimes the results of all the candidates are cancelled even though it may not be certain that every candidate is involved in cheating. However, irrespective of various measures and devices formulated to beat down cheating in examinations, the wave of examination misconduct in Nigerian schools at all levels has continued to increase (p. 3). It has therefore, become necessary to investigate invigilators' misconducts in examinations. This is because there is every likelihood that invigilator characteristics as it relates to examination invigilation would deter or encourage students' examination malpractice behaviour. Some of the invigilators' misconducts may be direct accomplice to students' examination malpractices. Some other invigilators' misconducts could create atmosphere conducive for students to cheat during examinations.

The purpose of this study was to ascertain invigilators' examination misconduct characteristics and their correlates of gender and experience of invigilators. The study was guided by one research question and two hypotheses. The research question was : What are the prevalent invigilators' examination misconduct characteristics in tertiary institutions in Imo State, Nigeria?

The hypotheses were as follows:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct characteristics.

2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of 'new' and 'older' invigilators concerning invigilation misconduct characteristics.

Method

This study was a descriptive survey using observational technique. This means that data for the study were obtained by observing invigilators during examinations. The study was carried out in four tertiary institutions in Imo State. These were Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Federal Polytechnic, Nekede, Imo State University, Owerri and Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. The population of the study comprised eighty lecturers. The instrument for data collection was a researcher's developed observationnaire entitled Examination Invigilation Misconduct Survey (EIMS). The instrument has sections A and B for the respondents. Section A was used to obtain information about the invigilators, such as gender and year of experience. Section B contained twenty-five items on invigilator's misconduct characteristics. The method of recording was tallying. The instrument was constructed by the researchers and validated by three experts who teach in the universities; one specialized in educational psychology and the other two in Measurement and Evaluation. They were given copies of the purpose and objectives of the research and a copy of the observationnaire and were requested to consider the relevance of the items to the research objectives and the adequacy of the items. Their comments helped in refining the items. Following their inputs, some items were modified while others were replaced. The observationnaire was assessed for reliability. It was used by two independent researchers to observe twenty invigilators over two examinations in a College of Education in Anambra State. The inter-rater correlation technique involving the two observers was applied. The researchers used Pearson's Product Moment Statistics to compute the index of relationship between the two observers. The correlation coefficient calculated was 0.84. This was considered high and adequately reliable for the study. The researchers observed the sampled invigilators during eight semesters' examinations. A total of eighty invigilators were observed. The observers posed as invigilators but attentively recorded any form of misconduct exhibited by the invigilators during the examination using the observational schedule. The data were presented in tables. Frequency counts were used to analyze the research questions. The hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

This section presents the results of the study according to the research questions and hypotheses

Research Question 1: What are the prevalent examination invigilators' misconduct characteristics in tertiary institutions?

The researchers observed the sampled invigilators during eight semesters' examinations. The frequencies of the occurrence of prevalent misconducts of invigilators are presented on the table 1.

Table 1: Observed examination invigilation misconducts

S/N	Characteristics of invigilator misconduct	Tallies	Frequencies
1	Late arrival of invigilator to examination	HHH HHH HHH	15
2	Starting the examination before the scheduled time	//	2
3	Stopping the examination before the scheduled time	/	1
4	Starting the examination later than the scheduled time	HHH	5
5	Extending the duration of examination time	HHH /	6
6	Incessant announcements	HHH HHH	9
7	Verbally harassing the students	HHH HHH	10
8	Noise making including use of phones	HHH HHH HHH HHH	18
9	Helping students to answer questions	HHH HHH HHH HHH	20
10	Failing to promptly attend to students' call for papers	HHH HHH HHH	15
11	Failing to properly package the scripts	//	2
12	Failing to properly secure the examination materials	///	3
13	Failing to take the scripts to the appropriate place quickly after examination	///	3
14	Physically molesting students	HHH	5
15	Tearing of students' scripts	HHH	4
16	Seeking inducement from students	//	2
17	Sleeping while on supervision	/	1
18	Sitting or standing tight thereby failing to move round to supervise	HHH //	7
19	Asking students to distribute examination materials	///	3
20	Failure to properly keep attendance records	///	3
21	Failure to check the identity of students	HHH	4
22	Engaging in prolonged reading during examination	HHH //	7
23	Writing during examination	//	2
24	Ignoring a student who commits malpractice	HHH HHH /	11
25	Permitting hawkers in and around the examination hall	HHH //	7

Results of data analysis presented in Table 1 showed varied frequencies of occurrence of twenty-five invigilator misconducts during examinations. The prominent misconducts included helping students to answer questions, noise making including use of phones, incessant announcements, late arrival of invigilators to examinations, failing to promptly attend to students' call for papers and ignoring students who commit examination malpractices. Others were verbally harassing and physically molesting the students, incessant announcements, sitting or standing tight and sleeping thereby failing to move round to supervise, engaging in prolonged reading and writing during examination, allowing hawkers in and around the examination hall, failure to check the identity of students failing to keep attendance records, failing to properly secure the examination materials and to take the scripts to the appropriate place quickly after examination.

Hypothesis I: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct characteristics.

The mean occurrence of examination misconducts of the male numbering thirty five and female numbering forty five invigilators were calculated. The means and standard deviation scores for the two groups were tested for significant difference using t-test. The summary is presented on table 2.

Table 2. Summary of t-test for significant difference between the male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct characteristics.

Group	N	\bar{X}	Std dev	t-cal	Level of significance	t-tab	Decision
Male	35	2.1	0.6	1.0	0.05	2.0	Not Significant
Female	45	2.2	0.4				

From table 2, the results of the t-test show that the calculated t-value is 1.0 whereas the table t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.0. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct characteristics. As a result of this, the null hypothesis was not rejected. It is proper to assert that there is no significant difference between the mean score of male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct characteristics.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of ‘new’ and ‘older’ invigilators concerning invigilation misconduct characteristics.

‘Older’ invigilators referred to invigilators who have spent up to and above 10years in teaching and supervising examinations in tertiary institutions. ‘New’ invigilators referred to invigilators who have spent less than ten years teaching and supervising examinations in tertiary institutions.

The mean misconduct characteristics of the ‘new’ and ‘older’ invigilators concerning invigilation misconduct characteristics were tested for significant difference using t-test statistics. The summary is presented in the table that follows.

Table 3. Summary of t-test for significant difference between the mean examination invigilation misconduct of the ‘new’ and ‘older’ invigilators.

Group	No	\bar{X}	Std. dev	t-cal	Level of significance	t-tab	Decision
‘Older’ invigilators	25	2.08	1.62				Significant
‘New’ invigilators	55	1.34	1.88	3.89	0.05	2.0	

As presented in table 3, the results of the t-test showed that the calculated t-value is 3.89 whereas the table t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.0. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the mean examination invigilation misconduct scores of the ‘new’ and ‘older’ invigilators. As a result of this, the null hypothesis was rejected hence it is proper to assert that there is a significant difference in examination invigilation misconducts of the ‘new’ and ‘older’ invigilators.

Discussion

The study found out that the prevalent invigilator misconducts during examinations included helping students to answer questions, noise making, frequently using phones, incessant announcements, late arrival of invigilators to examinations, failing to promptly attend to students’ call for papers and ignoring students who commit malpractice. Others were verbally harassing and physically molesting

the students, incessant announcements, sitting or standing tight and sleeping thereby failing to move round to supervise, engaging in prolonged reading and writing during examination, allowing hawkers in and around the examination hall, failure to check the identity of students failing to keep attendance records, failing to properly secure the examination materials and to take the scripts to the appropriate place quickly after examination. Some invigilators do not take examination very seriously. Some are totally absent during examinations while some come late. Yet some of the invigilators lack proper supervision manners. They verbally harass and physically molest students. Some tear students' answer scripts and some are on phone calls, some discuss with friends in a manner that constitutes noise in the examination hall. Some invigilators invite hawkers of snacks thereby turning the examination hall into a market place.

The findings are in line with Chioke (2008) who alleged that the sources of disturbances during examinations are not from the candidates only but also from both teachers and the school managements. It should be pointed out that in this age of mobile telecommunication, the misuse of cell phones could disturb the tranquil conduct of examinations.

Contrary to the positions of Olaniyi (2011), the study did not find any significant difference in the invigilator misconducts between male and female invigilators. However, the mean observed invigilator misconduct of the 'new' and 'older' invigilators were found to be statistically significantly different. There may not be any serious reason to expect a significant difference between the male and female invigilators except the argument by Olaniyi (2011) that female invigilators may be prone to late coming, unable to effectively circulate in the examination hall and face up some rough students who defy examination rules. It was also thought that the male invigilators would have a greater tendency to harass and molest students. However, Chioke (2008) noted that the occurrence of supervisor misconducts has no gender bias.

There is reason to accept the finding that a significant difference was found between the 'new' and 'older' invigilators concerning invigilation misconducts. The 'older' ones would have over the years gained experiences. Some may have been commended, cautioned and penalized for examination proper conducts or misconducts. Some have served in some examination related committees. These advantages are in favour of the 'older' invigilators. Decklan (2015) supported the finding and recommended that lecturers who have spent more years in the institutions should not leave examination supervision for the new ones.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are made.

1. The authorities of institutions should prescribe and take disciplinary actions against invigilators who fail to carry out their invigilation responsibilities properly.
2. The management of institutions should avoid checking payment of school fees when examinations are going on.
3. The examination halls should be made conducive for invigilators to minimize movements and rearrangement of seats.
4. The management of institutions should organize orientation programmes for invigilators especially the 'new' staff on proper invigilation conducts.
5. The older and more experienced lecturers should participate in invigilating examinations and not leave it for 'new' lecturers. They should be made invigilation teams.

Conclusion

The study investigated prevalent misconducts among invigilators during examinations. It was carried out in four tertiary institutions in Imo State. These were Federal University of Technology, Owerri,

Federal Polytechnic, Nekede, Owerri, Imo State University, Owerri and Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. One research question and two hypotheses were used to guide the study. Eighty invigilators were observed during a total of eight examinations. The instrument for data collection was a researchers' developed observationnaire entitled 'Examination Invigilation Misconduct Survey' (EIMS). The instrument was used to obtain information about the invigilators, such as gender and year of experience. It contained twenty five items on examination invigilation misconduct characteristics. Data were analyzed with frequency counts, mean and t- test statistics. The findings showed that the common misconducts included helping students to answer questions, noise making including use of cell phones, incessant announcements, late arrival of invigilators to examinations, failing to promptly attend to students' call for papers and ignoring students who commit malpractice. Others were verbally harassing and physically molesting the students, sitting or standing tight and sleeping thereby failing to move round to supervise the ongoing examinations, engaging in prolonged reading and writing during examination, allowing hawkers in and around the examination hall, failure to check the identity of students failing to keep attendance records, failing to properly secure the examination materials and to take the scripts to the appropriate place quickly after examination. It was found out that there was no significant difference between the male and female invigilators concerning examination invigilation misconduct. The study however, found a significant difference between the 'new' and 'old' invigilators in favour of the 'old' ones concerning examination misconducts. On the basis of the findings, it was recommended that the authorities of institutions should prescribe and take disciplinary actions against invigilators who fail to carry out their invigilation responsibilities properly and the managements should avoid checking payment of school fees when examination is going on. It was also recommended that the examination halls should be made conducive for invigilators to minimize movements and re-arrangement of seats, and the management of institutions should organize orientation programmes for invigilators especially the 'new' staff on proper invigilation conducts.

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